

Synthesis of Heterocyclics via Enamines. Part IV*. Reaction of Ethyl- β -anilinoacrylate with 2-Methyl-4-oxopent-2-yl-isothiocyanate

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The title reaction gave 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4, 6, 6-trimethyl-3, 6-dihydropyrimidine and 2-anilino-4, 4, 6-trimethyl 1, 3-thiazine as major and minor products respectively.

IGNATOVA and coworkers¹ had reported the formation of 2-anilino-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1, 3-thiazine (I, R=C₆H₅) by heating 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4, 6, 6-trimethyl-3,6-dihydropyrimidine (II, R=C₆H₅)

in hydrochloric acid but in our hands the same operation furnished a much lower melting product². Clarke³ had recently reported the formation of acrylonitriles in similar reactions of acids with pyri-

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* Part III : H. Singh, S. Singh and R. K. Mehta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14 B, 215.

midines. In view of both these observations, an alternate synthesis of I ($R=C_6H_5$) was warranted. During the condensations of 2-methyl-4-oxopent-2-yl-isothiocyanate (III) and ammonia with ethyl- β -aminocrotonate^{4,6} 2-amino-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-thiazine (I, $R=H$) was formed along with 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,4-dihydropyrimidine (II, $R=H$). Here we report our results of the studies on the condensation of ethyl- β -anilino crotonate (IV) and (III) carried with the aim of synthesising I ($R=C_6H_5$). The product comprised of a minor component A, a major component B and ethyl acetoacetate (glc). The major component was identified as II ($R=C_6H_5$)⁶. In case of component A, its molecular weight of 232 (mass spectrum) showed that it was isomeric with (II, $R=C_6H_5$) and was assigned the structure, 2-anilino-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-thiazine I, ($R=C_6H_5$) which was supported by the following spectral observations. Its i.r. spectrum indicated the presence of guanidino, $>C=N$ (1690)⁷. Its n.m.r. spectrum (CCl_4): δ 1.20 (6H, s, $>C(CH_3)_2$), 1.95 (3H, s, $-CH_3$), 4.50 (1H, s, $>CH-$) and 7.0-7.2 (m, 5H, aromatic protons) accounted for all the protons in I ($R=C_6H_5$).

In comparison with the preferred formation of I ($R=H$)⁴ from ethyl- β -aminocrotonate and (III) in solvents of high dielectric constant similar changes in the reaction medium did not result in any spectacular change in the composition of product mixture of I and II ($R=C_6H_5$) (Table). Further in contrast to the reaction of ammonia with (III) where the formation of both pyrimidine and thiazine derivative was recorded⁴, in the condensation of aniline and (III) the presence of thiazine could not be detected.

From the three reaction pathways⁴ depicted for the reaction of III and ethyl- β -anilino crotonate (Scheme 1), route (a) was ruled out as 1,4-diazocine derivative (VIII) was not formed⁸. The pathways (c) and (b) would form II ($R=C_6H_5$) and I ($R=C_6H_5$) through the intermediacy of V and VI respectively. In solvents of higher dielectric constant⁴ VI would provide I ($R=C_6H_5$) more easily but the composition of the product mixture did not change with the change of solvent (table). Hence, contrary to the reaction of ethyl- β -aminocrotonate and I, here, the intermediacy of V was preferred over that of VI and the solvents of higher dielectric constant could not accomplish a selective formation of I ($R=C_6H_5$)⁹. It might be concluded that in such reactions of isothiocyanato ketones with ethyl- β -aminocrotonates, the structures and the fates of the intermediates, involved decide the reaction pathway.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes. Infrared spectra were recorded in $CHCl_3$ solution

on Specord 71 IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in ethanol on CZ VSU-2 spectrophotometer. N.M.R. spectra were recorded on Tesla BS 487 C, 80 MHz instrument using TMS as internal reference. Mass spectrum was recorded at 70 eV ionizing voltage on Hitachi Perkin Elmer RMU-60 mass spectrometer. For tlc, plates were coated with silica gel G and spots were developed in an iodine chamber.

1. Condensation of ethyl- β -anilino crotonate (IV) and 2-Methyl-4-oxopent-2-yl isothiocyanate (III):

Ethyl- β -anilino crotonate (2.05g, 0.01 mole) was mixed with 2-methyl-4-oxopent-2-yl-isothiocyanate (1.57g, 0.01 mole) and the reaction mixture was heated at 100°. The progress of the reaction was monitored on tlc and it took 30 minutes for its completion. The reaction mixture was cooled and white crystals of 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4,6,6-trimethyl-1,4-dihydropyrimidine separated out. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the residue was washed with ether. The ethereal washings were mixed with the supernatant liquid. On tlc it showed two components which were isolated by chromatography over neutral alumina. This mother liquor on glc exhibited a peak with retention time equal to that of ethyl acetoacetate.

The component A (R_f 0.70, $CHCl_3$) was eluted with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and was crystallized from benzene, m.p. 128°-9°, M^+ , m/e 232. ν^{CHCl_3} 3150-2925, 1690, 1550, 1470, 1330 cm^{-1} , ν^{EtOH} 304 (ϵ 21785) nm. N.M.R. (CCl_4): δ 1.20 (6H, s, $>C(CH_3)_2$), δ 1.95 (3H, s, $-CH_3$), δ 4.50 (1H, s, $CH-$), δ 7.0-7.2 (5H, m, aromatic protons). Mass spectrum: M^+ m/e 232, m/e 217 (M^+-CH_3), m/e 82 (217-PhNCS), m/e 42 ($82-CH_3-C\equiv CH$), m/e 97 (223-PhNCS), m/e 57 (97- $CH_3C\equiv CH$) (Found: C, 66.82; H, 7.2, N, 11.90. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2S$ requires C, 67.2; H, 6.90; N, 12.1).

The component B (R_f 0.5, $CHCl_3$) was eluted with benzene and was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 202°-4°, ν^{CHCl_3} 3175, 3080, 2950, 1680, 1630, 1590 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. δ 1.32 (6H, s, $>C(CH_3)_2$), δ 1.46 (3H, s, $-CH_3$), δ 4.76 (1H, s, $CH-$), δ 7.3 (5H, m). λ^{EtOH} 275 (ϵ 12482) nm. (Found: C, 66.52; H, 6.94; N, 11.79. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2S$ requires C, 67.2; H, 6.90; N, 12.1). It was identical with an authentic sample of 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4,6,6-trimethyl-3,6-dihydropyrimidine (R_f ; mmp; i.r.).

2. Condensation of IV and III in different solvents:

The solutions of equivalent amounts of (IV) and (III) (0.01 mole each) in benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetonitrile and ether were refluxed. The

completion of reaction took approximately 1 hour in each case as monitored on tlc. The solvents were removed and the residue were dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) separately. These solutions were appropriately diluted for recording their quantitative electronic spectra and the percentage compositions in each case were determined from the absorbance at 275 and 305 nm (Table).

TABLE

Percentage compositions of the products (II) and (I) in reactions of ethyl- β -anilino crotonate with 2-methyl-4-oxo-pent-2-yl-isothiocyanate in various solvents.

Solvent	II	I
Ether	88	12
Chloroform	82	18
Ethyl acetate	90	10
Benzene	89.5	10.5
Acetonitrile	89.5	10.5

3. Condensation of aniline and III :

Equivalent amounts of aniline and III were mixed and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for approximately 1 hour during which the

reaction was complete (tlc). The reaction product comprised of (II) only and (I) was not detected (tlc).

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9. It was envisaged that the use of polar solvents in this reaction could exclusively provide I(R = C₆H₅) as the formation of II(R = C₆H₅) was not possible.